

Title:

Development of Graphics Modular System for Virtual Machine Tools

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Abstract: In recent years, many parts are directly milled by using machine tools. In order to ensure accuracy and safety in processing, workpieces must be confirmed via simulation of virtual machine tools before machining. Therefore, it is very important to simulate before machining, and it also can be used as a teaching and training practices.

This study is to develop 3D simulation software of virtual machine tools by Borland C++ Builder. There are different types of virtual machine tools constructed in the program. In addition, we also develop the modular construction procedures for users to correctly create virtual machine tools using this simple graphical way. In the construction procedures, one can learn the concepts and operation of machine tools. The virtual machine tools can be completed according to the sequence of actions within the program. Applying the proposed graphics modular system to create virtual machine tools, it can improve inconvenience of original construction approaches and increase the applications of simulation software. Therefore, users can quickly know and learn the presented system in this thesis.

Keywords: virtual machine tool, graphics construction, modular

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